
Willingness of Indigenous Students in Communication Using Filipino Language

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ABSTRACT: The willingness to use a second language in communication is a challenge faced by indigenous students, resulting in a lack of self-confidence, difficulty in finding appropriate words, and anxiety that affects the lack of interest in engaging in conversations. This research aims to identify the willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication. The study utilized descriptive research involving (N=96) indigenous college students from UM Digos who participated in the adopted questionnaires. Mean, frequency distribution and t-tests were used as statistical tests. The survey results showed that the willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication is at a high level, indicating that it is frequently observed. However, the researchers encourage students, teachers, and staff to consistently use the Filipino language, both inside and outside the school. This serves as a way to maintain their willingness to communicate using the Filipino language at a high level.

KEYWORDS: willingness, communication, Filipino language, descriptive research, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

The willingness to use a second language in communication is a challenge faced by indigenous students (Bonifacio & Gersava, 2020; Edgerton, 2020; Machinyise, 2018; Tolentino, 2017). The lack of self-confidence, difficulty in finding appropriate words, and anxiety are just a few factors that affect the lack of interest in engaging in conversations (Bator, 2016). Furthermore, problems or difficulties in speaking English result in a lack of interest in learning (Andreou, 2006, as cited by Wannaruk & Lie, 2019). Indigenous students with speaking difficulties face even greater challenges due to their home dialect of Tagalog (Leaño, Rabi, & Piragasam, 2019). Aside from the issues related to speaking English, they also struggle to comprehend lessons and express themselves in the classroom.

The differences in linguistic usage, the use of students' native languages, and proper pausing methods are challenges that make communication difficult for students (Shen & Chiu, 2019). On the other hand, indigenous students in Colombia are concerned about the gradual loss of their language due to the dominant use of the Spanish language (Wilches, Medina, & Gutierrez, 2018). This is one of the issues faced by indigenous university students, where they have limited opportunities to use their dialect and expand their language knowledge (Londoño, 2017). Furthermore, this research reveals that the indigenous communities in Bukidnon, specifically the Manobo, Talaandig, and Maramag, experience difficulties in using and preserving their language (Casas 2020; Bonifacio & Gersava, 2020). On the other hand, young students from EFL Turkish show interest in using a second language in communication compared to older students (Duman, 2020). Similarly, indigenous young students from Australia also exhibit a readiness to use the English language in communication compared to older indigenous students (Smith & Walton, 2018). This is because their willingness to engage in conversations is higher when using the English language in communication.

The new generation, youth aged 3 to 19 years old, lacks proficiency in speaking due to a lack of interest in using their dialect, prejudice, and linguistic convergence. In comparison to other dominant languages such as Cebuano, Tagalog-based Filipino, and English, the Binukid language is not commonly used (Casas, 2020; Bonifacio & Gersava, 2020). Furthermore, it was identified in the study by Muhammad and Abdul Rahim (2022) that indigenous females are more interested than males in conversing using the English language. This aligns with the findings of Arshad, Khan, and Rehman (2015), where Pakistani women exhibit a greater willingness to use English compared to their native language which is Urdu, indicating a more enthusiastic use and learning of the English language without anxiety during English conversations.

This study is anchored in Gardner's (2001) Integrative Motivation Theory, which suggests that an individual with high motivation to use a second language demonstrates a willingness to engage in conversations using that second language.

However, the mentioned studies have focused only on the English language. In the Filipino language, there are few or no studies that investigate the factors affecting the willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language, especially in

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communication. Therefore, this study focuses on the Filipino language, specifically among indigenous students at UM Digos College.

The gathered results regarding the willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication will provide valuable global contributions to the literature. This will open doors to a deeper understanding of the importance of using one's native language and may serve as a model for other countries to value and maintain a high level of willingness to use their language, particularly in the aspect of communication. At the community level, the analysis of the native language aims to elevate understanding, and it is crucial for both public and private schools, especially at higher levels of education, to understand how to sustain the willingness to communicate among indigenous students in the school setting. This study holds significance for school administrators and teachers as it provides foundational information and valid results regarding the appropriate use and willingness to communicate using the Filipino language among students. The findings can give educators insights on how to maintain a high level of engagement among indigenous students in the classroom. This study is also valuable for indigenous college students, as the research directly focuses on their experiences. Additionally, it serves as a helpful resource for future researchers. The results and data from this study can be utilized for related research endeavors in the future.

Analyzing the willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication can assist the Department of Education in focusing more attention on the significance of indigenous students' preferences. It can provide valuable insights into the considerations that should be taken into account in communication. This research may address the lack of interest in conversing and draw attention to speech-related issues contributing to a lack of engagement in the classroom. Furthermore, this study can contribute to enhancing teachers' strategies for effective teaching, making the learning experience more engaging and interesting for indigenous students within the classroom.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This study aimed to identify the willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication. As an assurance, this study also intends to achieve the following:

1. To determine the demographic profile of the indigenous students using the Filipino language in communication:
 - 1.1 Gender;
 - 1.2 Age; and
 - 1.3 Tribal Affiliation.
2. To analyze the level of willingness of the indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication:
 - 2.1 The Importance of Learning and Using Filipino language in the classroom;
 - 2.2 The Usefulness of Communicating Using Filipino Language in the Classroom;
 - 2.3 Willingness to Communicate Using Filipino language in the Classroom;
 - 2.4 Vocabulary;
 - 2.5 Grammar;
 - 2.6 Pronunciation;
 - 2.7 Interlocutor;
 - 2.8 Motivation;
 - 2.9 Anxiety;
 - 2.10 Social Situation; and
 - 2.11 Topic of Interest.
3. To determine the level of willingness between indigenous male and female students to use the Filipino language in communication.

METHOD

Respondents

This study involves indigenous students currently enrolled in the academic year 2022-2023 at UM Digos College as respondents. It was conducted at UM Digos College, Brgy. Zone II, Roxas Extension, Digos City, Davao del Sur, Philippines. The research focuses on indigenous college students, with a total of ninety-six (N=96) participants. Universal sampling was employed, where all indigenous college students at UM Digos College served as respondents. This method greatly assisted the researchers in obtaining the most accurate sample representing the entire population of the study. The criteria for this study include the demographic profile of the participants, such as age, gender, and tribal affiliation.

Instrument

One of the survey instruments used to gather data was an adapted and enhanced questionnaire from the research paper of Rihardini, Yaniafari, and Mukminatien (2021) titled "Students' Willingness to Communicate using English: A Survey Study." It contained a total of nineteen (19) items, with two (2) focusing on the importance of language learning in the classroom, four (4) for

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effective language use in classroom communication, four (4) for language willingness in classroom communication, two (2) for vocabulary, two (2) for grammar, two (2) for pronunciation, four (4) for conversation, two (2) for motivation, four (4) for anxiety,

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	Indicates that the condition related to the level of speaking preference is always noticed.
3.40-4.19	High	Indicates that the condition related to speaking preference is often noticed.
2.60-3.39	Moderate	Indicates that the condition related to the level of speaking preference is sometimes noticed.
1.80-2.59	Low	Indicates that the condition related to the level of speaking preference is rarely noticed.
1.00-1.79	Very Low	Indicates that the condition related to the level of speaking preference is not noticed.

one (1) for situational factors, and two (2) for interest in the subject. In response to their answers, the researchers prepared answer keys for correct responses and scoring for the conducted survey. To describe the levels that emerged from the data, the following scaling and mean range were utilized.

Design and Procedure

This research employed a quantitative, non-experimental design, specifically descriptive research. Descriptive research aims to measure a population, situation, or phenomenon accurately and systematically (McCombes, 2019). This design is appropriate for this study as it seeks only to identify the level of willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication based on nineteen factors.

The researchers obtained a letter of approval for data collection and gathered records of indigenous students from the Office of Student Affairs to identify participants. Permission letters were provided to those who participated in the study. The researchers administered questionnaires to the identified sample size, and the completed papers were collected in preparation for data encoding and analysis. The researchers estimated that it would take about two weeks to complete the data collection for the research. One challenge faced by the researchers was coordinating the schedules and vacant times of indigenous students due to differing schedules and school days.

The collected data were recorded in Microsoft Excel and promptly submitted to the statistician. To ensure accurate and reliable results, the following statistical tools were utilized. The Mean was used to determine the level of preference of indigenous students in using the Filipino language in communication based on eleven factors: importance of language learning in class, effective language use in classroom communication, language preference in classroom communication, vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, conversation, motivation, anxiety, situational factors, and interest in the subject. Frequency distribution was employed to organize the count of indigenous students in each category of data collection. The T-test was employed to assess whether there was a statistically significant difference in the willingness to use the Filipino language in communication between indigenous female and male students, providing a quantitative measure of potential gender-related variations.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers conducted a thorough review of ethical standards for conducting research at UM Digos College, particularly in population management and non-restrictive data handling, based on the evaluation of proposals and standards in standardization, such as:

Voluntary Participation: Participants in this study were given voluntary consent without fear of any penalties or fines.

Privacy Act Confidentiality: Personal information of participants will remain private, and no data or documents will be released to the public.

Informed Consent Process: The questionnaires were administered with permission from the relevant authorities, and no questions were given consent if unauthorized.

Risk: The study does not involve any risky situations, such as experiencing physical, psychological, or socio-economic harm.

Data Collection: Participants were selected, and with written consent, provided appropriate responses for data gathering. The study will be conducted using a Survey Questionnaire distributed face-to-face by researchers with accompanying permission obtained from the participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic profile of the indigenous students

Age. Table 1 shows that the majority of respondents belonged to the age group 21-23, comprising 38.5% of the total. The 18-20 age group followed with 14.6%, while those aged 24 and above constituted 8.3%, indicating a lower number of respondents in this category.

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Gender. In terms of gender, Table 1 indicates that there were more female respondents compared to males. The number of female respondents was fifty-eight (N=58), representing 60.4%, while the number of male respondents was thirty-eight (N=38), constituting only 39.6%.

Tribal Affiliation. Table 1 further breaks down the indigenous students into sixteen ethnic groups (N=96). The Bagobo ethnic group had the highest number of respondents at 21%, followed by the B'laan at 13.6%, and the Manobo and Tagakaolo ethnic groups both at 12.5%. Other ethnic groups included Kagan and Mandaya at 9.4%, Tausog at 6.3%, Maranao and Kaolo at 3.1% each, Igorot at 2.1%, and Bol-anon, Kamayo, Lumad, Maguindanaw, Mansaka, and Sama, each at 1.0%. This indicates a lower number of respondents from these ethnic groups.

Table 1. Demographic profile of the indigenous students

Demographic Profile	<i>f</i>	%
Age		
21-23	67	69.8%
18-20	21	21.9%
24 and above	8	8.3%
Gender		
Babae	58	60.4%
Lalaki	38	39.6%
Tribal Affiliation		
Bagobo	21	21.9%
B'laan	13	13.6%
Manobo	12	12.5%
Tagakaolo	12	12.5%
Kagan	9	9.4%
Mandaya	9	9.4%
Tausog	6	6.3%
Maranao	3	3.1%
Kaolo	3	3.1%
Igorot	2	2.1%
Mansaka	1	1.0%
Bol-anon	1	1.0%
Kamayo	1	1.0%
Lumad	1	1.0%
Maguindanaw	1	1.0%
Sama	1	1.0%
Total	96	100%

The level of willingness of Indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication

Table 2 presents the data on the willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication, providing an overall mean score. The willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication yielded a mean score of ($\bar{x} = 4.03$; $SD = 0.39$). This indicates that the condition related to the willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication is frequently observed. The mentioned overall mean score is the result of the collected data provided by respondents for each item regarding the willingness of indigenous students to use the

Table 2. The level of willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication

Indicators	Mean	SD
The Importance of Learning and Using Filipino language in the classroom	4.36	0.622
The Usefulness of Communicating Using Filipino Language in the Classroom	4.23	0.82
Willingness to Communicate Using Filipino language in the Classroom	3.81	0.736
Vocabulary	3.98	0.696
Grammar	4.13	0.654

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Pronunciation	4.02	0.605
Interlocutor	3.74	0.544
Motivation	4.05	0.679
Anxiety	3.93	0.648
Social Situation	3.93	0.714
Topic of Interest	4.00	0.837
Kaburuan	4.03	0.39

Filipino language in communication. However, the willingness of indigenous students to use the Filipino language in communication among UM Digos College students is frequently observed.

Based on the research results, the readiness and willingness to use their language were identified among indigenous students from India. Furthermore, they are encouraged to use their language when they are interested in topics related to their culture (Sharma & Das, 2017). Additionally, when students feel included and their dialect is valued, they are inclined to use their language and exhibit a willingness to communicate within the class (Bear, King, & O'Leary, 2021). Nevertheless, as cited by Bear (2021), many indigenous students still face challenges in using their dialect in class, such as encountering disapproval from teachers or classmates or feeling the need to code-switch. Therefore, the willingness to use their language was associated with the highest levels of self-esteem, cultural closeness, community connection, and academic success (Johnson, 2022).

The Importance of Learning and Using Filipino language in the classroom. Table 2 showed that the first indicator of the importance of learning and using the Filipino language in the classroom obtained the highest level of preference among native students in the use of Filipino in communication ($\bar{x} = 4.36$; $SD = 0.622$). This indicates that the condition related to the importance of learning and using the Filipino language in the classroom is consistently observed. This implies that students at UM Digos College value studying and using the Filipino language in class.

Language is a key to understanding within the classroom (Benson, 2005), as mentioned in Dominguez's study (2022). The use of a second language in classroom communication holds profound importance in shaping students' knowledge and development (Bautista, 2017). Additionally, it provides a pathway to more effective communication and cooperation. Liang and Brown (2019) agree that by focusing on the use of one's language, communication within the classroom becomes more effective, leading to a quicker understanding of concepts and ideas and opening the door to higher levels of knowledge.

The Usefulness of Communicating Using Filipino language in the classroom. Table 2 showed that the second indicator which is the usefulness of communicating using the Filipino language in the classroom garnered the highest level of willingness among native students to communicate ($\bar{x} = 4.36$; $SD = 0.622$). This suggests that the condition related to the usefulness of communicating using the Filipino language in the classroom is consistently observed. This implies that UM Digos College students exhibit effective use of the Filipino language in classroom communication.

Based on the study's results, Swain (1995) emphasized, as mentioned in the research of Rihardini, Yaniafari, and Mukminatien (2021), that the effective use of a second language in the classroom allows for in-depth understanding and thoughtful reflection on lessons. Furthermore, having a proper command of one's language leads to a profound understanding of the subjects studied by students. Similarly, in the study conducted by Villanueva, Bawing, Garcia, Paez, Meyor, and Midel (2020), effective use of a second language creates a connection between teachers and students in expressing ideas and thoughts, where good communication leads to understanding among students.

Willingness to communicate using the Filipino language in the classroom. Table 2 shows that the third indicator which is the willingness to communicate using the Filipino language in the classroom obtained a high level of willingness among native students in language use ($\bar{x} = 3.81$; $SD = 0.736$). This suggests that the condition related to the Willingness to communicate using the Filipino language in the classroom is frequently observed. This implies that the students of UM Digos College exhibit a preference for using the Filipino language in classroom communication.

In a study conducted by Khudobina, Hopiaynen, and Bondarenko (2019), various researchers, including Kamprasertwong, Mahdi, Liu, Dewaele, and others, explored how personal factors (individual background, personality traits, and communication strategies) influence the willingness to engage and interact with each other in English speech (Jean-Marc & Taghreed, 2015). On the other hand, the study by Barjesteh, Vaseghi, and Neissi (2012) investigated the relationship between the willingness of students in Iran to communicate, both inside and outside the classroom, and language learning orientation. The results showed that language orientation indicates a willingness to converse outside the classroom compared to within the academic setting (Mahdi, 2014). Similarly, in Borkowska's research (2022), it was found that students are interested in engaging in conversation only when they are familiar with the situation, and their interest in speaking decreases otherwise. Language orientation indicates a willingness to converse outside the classroom compared to within the academic setting (Mahdi, 2014).

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Vocabulary. Table 2 showed that the fourth indicator, vocabulary, received a high level of willingness among native students to use the Filipino language in communication ($\bar{x} = 3.98$; $SD = 0.696$). This suggests that the condition related to vocabulary is frequently observed. This implies that the students of UM Digos College exhibit a willingness to use an extensive vocabulary.

Vocabulary is considered crucial for successful second language learning (Schmitt, 2000), as mentioned in Lin's study (2015). Students with a strong vocabulary foundation may experience an accelerated learning curve in the subsequent stages of language learning and successfully develop skills in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Additionally, vocabulary serves as the foundation for real-life communication. The more vocabulary a student understands, the better their expressions will be, as Gilakjani and Sabouri (2016) believe that a weak vocabulary in a language results in poor listening comprehension. Therefore, Kepinska (2017) stated that learning words is undeniably one of the most important aspects of acquiring a new language. Tanaka (2017) mentioned that students with the ability to learn a language enjoy studying new words and vocabulary.

Grammar. Table 2 showed that the fifth indicator, grammar, received a high level of preference among native students in using the Filipino language in communication ($\bar{x} = 4.13$; $SD = 0.654$). This suggests that the condition related to grammar is frequently observed. This implies that the students of UM Digos College exhibit a preference for using proper grammar.

The results of the study align with the research conducted by Syam (2017), emphasizing the significance of grammar in language learning. He added that without proficiency and deep knowledge of grammar, students can expect errors in both writing and speaking. Related to this, the results of the research by Duman (2020) indicated that foreign students consider the study of grammar as a foundation, enabling them to construct appropriate sentences for communication. Therefore, a lack of knowledge in grammar formation is indicative of inactive communication. Thus, the support from Bayou (2015) for proficiency in learning grammar lies in the ability to have meaningful communication, making conversations more engaging.

Pronunciation. Table 2 showed that the sixth indicator, pronunciation, received a high level of willingness among native students to use the Filipino language in communication ($\bar{x} = 4.02$; $SD = 0.605$). This suggests that the condition related to pronunciation is frequently observed. This implies that the students of UM Digos College exhibit a willingness for proper pronunciation.

Based on the study results of Chang and Chang (2023), it is evident that correct pronunciation is a crucial aspect of communication. Students with good pronunciation are better understood by native speakers and other students. Furthermore, students with confidence in their pronunciation are more likely to participate in discussions. The proper pronunciation of words serves as a pathway for students to learn about their correct usage (Peña, Cura, & Galamay, 2023). According to them, this can enhance social interactions among students as they become adaptable to various communication styles. For language teachers, correct pronunciation can be a means to assess a student's speaking skills, which can be utilized in lesson planning, preparation for language activities, and selecting appropriate teaching materials (Dominguez, 2022).

Interlocutor. Table 2 showed that the seventh indicator, interlocutor, received a high level of willingness among native students to use the Filipino language in communication ($\bar{x} = 3.74$; $SD = 0.544$). This suggests that the condition related to the interlocutor is frequently observed. This implies that the students of UM Digos College exhibit a preference for interpersonal interaction or conversation.

According to the research results, students are willing to engage in conversations with classmates they are familiar with, where familiarity has a significant influence on second language use for speaking purposes (Kang, 2005, as cited in Mystkowska-Wiertelak & Pawlak, 2017). Additionally, the sense of belongingness, particularly in motivating students to actively participate in an activity, is crucial (Cao & Philp, 2006; Nagy & Nikolov, 2007; Pawlak & Mystkowska-Wiertelak, 2015). Students may also be encouraged to discuss a topic when there are varying opinions among classmates (Riasati, 2018; Riasati & Rahimi, 2018).

Motivation. Table 2 indicates that the eighth indicator, motivation, received a higher level of willingness among native students to use the Filipino language in communication ($\bar{x} = 4.05$; $SD = 0.679$). This suggests that the condition related to motivation is frequently observed. This implies that the students of UM Digos College exhibit motivation.

Motivation is a crucial element in learning a new language and should be developed not only internally but also externally (Zrekat, Bukar, & Latif, 2016). The study results correlate with Hashimoto's research (2019), which indicates that frequent use of a second language results in high motivation to use the second language in communication, with motivation being the strongest predictor of conversation. Nevertheless, the results also highlight the essential role of teachers, where students are expected to cultivate their motivation and enhance their willingness to use the second language in communication with classmates (Zarrinabadi, Ketabi, & Abdi, 2014).

Anxiety. Table 2 indicates that the ninth indicator, anxiety, received a high level of willingness among native students to use the Filipino language in communication ($\bar{x} = 3.93$; $SD = 0.648$). This suggests that the condition related to anxiety is frequently observed. This implies that the students of UM Digos College exhibit anxiety.

Language anxiety refers to the fear or apprehension experienced by a student when expected to use the English language (Kilag, Catubay, Balicoco, Contado, Yray, & Bendanillo, 2023). For them, language anxiety can be categorized into four aspects:

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fear of communication, fear of negative evaluation, anxiety in tests, and nervousness in using English inside the classroom. One of the primary causes of anxiety when using English is the fear of negative evaluation from teachers. This is supported by the study of Rihardini, Yaniafari, and Mukminatien (2021), which revealed that students from Turkey prefer their teachers not to correct them every time they make a mistake because they believe that their teacher's correction of their mistakes is the main reason for their anxiety.

Social Situation. Table 2 indicates that the tenth indicator, social situation, received a high level of willingness among native students to use the Filipino language in communication ($\bar{x} = 3.93$; $SD = 0.714$). This suggests that conditions related to the social context are frequently observed. This implies that the students of UM Digos College exhibit a willingness to accept social situations.

The interaction in teaching refers to the teacher-student relationship and student participation, closely related to teacher support (Pöysä, 2019). Therefore, interpersonal communication can be considered a crucial factor in analyzing students within the classroom. The interaction between teachers and students can lead to active student participation (del Arco, 2021; Pöysä et al., 2019), improve learning motivation, convey success and self-efficacy (Li & Yang, 2021), enhance leadership skills (Zhan et al., 2021), and promote effective teaching in classrooms (Li & Yang, 2021; Weizheng, 2019).

Topic of Interest. Table 2 indicates that the eleventh indicator, the topic of interest, received a high level of willingness among native students to use the Filipino language in communication ($\bar{x} = 4.00$; $SD = 0.837$) This suggests that the condition related to the topic of interest is frequently observed. This implies that the students of UM Digos College exhibit a willingness to explore topics of interest.

According to the results, young students in Korea show a willingness to engage in conversations when interested in the topic being discussed (Park, 2023). He emphasized that students become more open to using the English language when they are interested in the topic. Additionally, based on the results of Riasati (2012), as cited in the study of Rihardini, Yaniafari, and Mukminatien (2021), students are more inclined to engage in conversation when they are familiar with the topic, believing that the topic greatly influences their desire to converse. Furthermore, when students have sufficient information or knowledge about a topic, their willingness to engage in conversation increases.

Level of willingness between indigenous males and female students to use the Filipino language in communication.

Table 3 presents the level of willingness of native students to use the Filipino language in communication-based on gender. According to the results, there is a significant difference in the overall willingness level of native students to use the Filipino language in communication when analyzed by gender ($t(94) = -2.69$, $p = 0.008$). Furthermore, indicator 3 ($t(94) = -2.13$, $p = 0.036$), indicator 7 ($t(94) = 0.044$), indicator 9 ($t(94) = -2.25$, $p = 0.027$), and indicator 11 ($t(94) = -2.29$, $p = 0.024$) have p-values lower than 0.05, indicating a significant difference between male and female students based on those indicators.

Table 3: Level of willingness between indigenous male and female students to use the Filipino language in communication

Indicators	Gender	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	p
Indicator 1	Female	58	4.34	0.691	-0.5503	94	0.583
	Male	38	4.41	0.505			
Indicator 2	Female	58	4.14	0.853	-1.3666	94	0.175
	Male	38	4.38	0.755			
Indicator 3	Female	58	3.69	0.678	-2.129	94	0.036
	Male	38	4.01	0.787			
Indicator 4	Female	58	3.98	0.688	0.0622	94	0.951
	Male	38	3.97	0.716			
Indicator 5	Female	58	4.06	0.649	-1.2979	94	0.197
	Male	38	4.24	0.655			
Indicator 6	Female	58	3.94	0.6	-1.5317	94	0.129
	Male	38	4.13	0.6			
Indicator 7	Female	58	3.65	0.541	-2.0397	94	0.044
	Male	38	3.88	0.525			
Indicator 8	Female	58	3.97	0.674	-1.5558	94	0.123
	Male	38	4.18	0.672			
Indicator 9	Female	58	3.82	0.625	-2.2489	94	0.027
	Male	38	4.11	0.65			
Indicator 10	Female	58	3.83	0.704	-1.7026	94	0.092
	Male	38	4.08	0.712			
Indicator 11	Female	58	3.84	0.79	-2.2949	94	0.024
	Male	38	4.24	0.86			
Total	Female	58	3.94	0.391	-2.6928	94	0.008
	Male	38	4.15	0.355			

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The study by Melissa and Ariel (2020) identified no significant difference in the willingness level of native female and male students to use the Filipino language in communication. They added that there are variations in the specific contexts of communication, where female students show interest in informal contexts, while male students tend to be interested in formal communication.

On the other hand, the results of the research by Tannenbaum and Tahar (2008), as mentioned in the study by Aliakbari, Kamangar, and Khany (2016), indicate that the willingness of female and male students to engage in conversations depends on the language used. Male students are inclined to engage in conversations both inside and outside the school when using their first language, unlike female students who prefer using their second language compared to their native language. This preference is attributed to their belief that they can express their ideas and opinions more freely without fear and anxiety when using a second language.

CONCLUSION

This study reveals that the majority of participants are native Bagobo individuals who exhibit a higher level of willingness to use the Filipino language in communication. The research, conducted mainly with native females aged 21–23, indicates a significant difference in the preference level between male and female native students for using the Filipino language in communication. Ultimately, this study is anchored in Gardner's (2001) Integrative Motivation Theory, as high motivation for using a second language signifies an inclination to engage in conversations using that language. According to this theory, individuals are intrinsically motivated to learn and use a second language when they perceive it as a means of integrating into a particular social or cultural group. High motivation in this context signifies a genuine inclination to immerse oneself in conversations and interactions facilitated by the second language, reflecting a broader commitment to understanding and being a part of the linguistic and cultural context associated with the language.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Institutions can use the study results as a basis for further research to assess the confidence of native students in speaking and their readiness to use the Filipino language in communication. Encourage students, teachers, and staff to consistently use the Filipino language both inside and outside the school, fostering a high preference for engaging in conversations using the Filipino language.

Implement actions within the institution to promote the use of the Filipino language. This can guide students, faculty, and staff in the proper use of the Filipino language, contributing to maintaining a high preference for engaging in conversations using the Filipino language.

Researchers recommend that GEFil teachers create rubrics for activities related to oral recitations or speaking-related tasks. This can help teachers identify the willingness or readiness of students to use the Filipino language in communication.

Considering the study's findings that native students exhibit high anxiety when using the Filipino language in communication, researchers suggest implementing programs to adequately develop and prepare native students for activities related to communication.

In courses where Filipino is included, the language to be used should be clearly stated in the syllabus. For courses not specifically designated as Filipino, the use of the mother tongue or English may be appropriate.

Lastly, this study can be used as a basis for conducting research in other locations or institutions connected to the preference for using the Filipino language in communication-based on their curriculum, using different methods and instruments that may yield new results.

POLICY ON THE USE OF FILIPINO LANGUAGE: USE OF FILIPINO LANGUAGE BY STUDENTS, FACULTY, AND STAFF OF UM DIGOS COLLEGE

I. Introduction

The Filipino language is not just a language; it is an integral part of our identity as a nation. It serves as a tool for unity and appreciation of our culture. In schools, the teaching and use of the Filipino language are of profound importance, not only in developing communication skills but also in shaping the identity of students. This program will discuss the steps and methods for how the use of the Filipino language can be effectively implemented within UM Digos College.

II. Objectives

The researcher proposes the implementation of the use of the Filipino language within the institution to guide teachers, students, faculty, and staff in the proper use of the Filipino language inside and outside the school. It is also suggested that the use of the Filipino language be promoted to cultivate and maintain a high regard for its usage, contributing to its enrichment as a language of communication. The researchers believe that the study conducted is valuable because the use of the Filipino language is a way to preserve and enhance the language. Moreover, it serves as a foundation for developing a culture of communication within and outside the school. The proposed student activities developed by the researchers will serve as a basis.

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III. Implementation Steps

- Mondays are significant days for everyone. Everyone is encouraged to use the Filipino language when conversing with peers, asking questions to faculty staff, and chatting with colleagues or classmates. It is a day of valuing and giving importance to the language that binds us all.
- Starting at the entrance gate, students, faculty, and staff will begin using Filipino when talking to the guards stationed there. This can be demonstrated through greetings or simple exchanges of pleasantries.
- This activity will start at 7:00 in the morning and end at 5:30 in the afternoon.
- The Kitkat Village, student lounge, and libraries will have signs reminding everyone to speak in Filipino during discussions or conversations in each meeting.

IV. Program Implementation

TIME	LOCATION	SIGNAGES	LANGUAGE TO BE USED
7:00-5:30	KIT-KAT VILLAGE	" <i>Wikang atin, gamitin natin</i> "	FILIPINO
7:00-5:30	ISDAAN(student lounge)	" <i>Uy! Magsalita ng naaayon sa wika</i> "	Filipino/Mother Tongue
7:00-5:30	LIBRARY	" <i>Ipagmalaki ang sariling wika</i> "	FILIPINO

V. CONCLUSION

Through the proper implementation and use of the Filipino language in the school, students, faculty, and all members of the institution will gain a deeper understanding of our culture, history, and the identity of the Philippines. Teaching the Filipino language is not only the responsibility of teachers but of the entire community because it opens doors to higher levels of knowledge and understanding. Through this program, the Filipino language will serve as a pathway to more meaningful learning and the identity of every Filipino. Above all, this program will pave the way to keeping our heritage language alive.

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